

MANAGEMENT OF GROUNDNUT FUNGAL FOLIAR DISEASES WITH FUNGICIDES

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Abstract

The field experiment was conducted at Oilseeds Research Station, Jalgaon during Kharif 2016-17, 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 to study the efficacy of six fungicides on fungal foliar diseases and yield of groundnut. The results indicated that Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + Foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS recorded the significantly least PDI of Late leaf spot at 60 DAS (24.16%) at 90 DAS (37.50%) and rust at 90 DAS (19.44%). The significantly highest pod yield (1399.67 kg / ha) and haulm yield (2729.67 kg / ha) was also recorded by seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + Foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS.

Keywords - Fungicides, Groundnut, LLS and Rust.

Introduction

Groundnut is also known as peanut or earthnut or money nut is a member of family Papilionaceae, largest and most important of the three divisions of Leguminosae. The botanical name of Groundnut, (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is derived from two Greek words, *Arachis* (arachos) meaning a 'weed' and hypogaea meaning 'below ground'. According to botanist, a more popular name for groundnut would be ground pea because groundnut is a pea and not a nut. The term 'nut' has perhaps been added, since the pea has a shell and flavour similar to the shells of many true nuts. It is native to South America, originated between Southern Bolivia and Northern Argentina, from where it spread throughout the new world. Groundnut was introduced in India by around 16th century by the Portuguese. It is grown under a wide range of environmental conditions encompassing latitudes between 40° South and 40° North of the equator. There are a few economically important foliar fungal diseases, such as early and late leaf spots commonly called as tikka disease and groundnut rust. Late leaf spot caused by *Phaeoisariopsis personata* and rust caused by *Puccinia arachidis* are commonly present wherever groundnut is grown. As the area under groundnut is predominant in kharif (rainy) season the foliar diseases like late leaf spot and rust may cause yield losses up to 50% in the semi-arid tropics. In India, late leaf spot is more severe than early leaf spot (Ghewande, 1990; Anonymous, 1993). It causes severe defoliation and reduces pod yields by more than 50% if the crop is not protected with chemicals (Shew *et al.*, 1988). The fungicides are the most common tools for controlling disease losses. An effective control measures for these economically important foliar fungal diseases is essential to minimize cost of production. In this view the present study

was planned to find out effective control measures against major foliar diseases i.e. late leaf spot and rust of groundnut.

Material and method

The experiment was conducted during Kharif 2016-17, 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 at the Experiential Farm of Oilseeds Research Station, Jalgaon. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with the variety JL-501 following the recommended spacing of 30 x 10cm and was replicated thrice. The treatments comprised of seven (six fungicides including control) viz., T₁ : Seed treatment of Carbendazim @ 2 g/kg seed + Spray of Mancozeb 2.0 g/(0.2%) at 40 and 65 DAS , T₂ : Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS, T₃ : Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Pyraclostrobin 5% + Metiram 55% WG @ 2 g/L (0.12%) at 40 and 65 DAS, T₄ : Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystrobin 25% WG @ 1.32 g/L (0.035%) at 40 and 65 DAS, T₅ : Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63% @ 2 g/L at 40 and 65 DAS, T₆ : Seed treatment of Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds and T₇: Control (Water spray).

Collection of Experimental Data**Disease Severity**

Severity of fungal foliar diseases viz., late leaf spot and rust were recorded in each treatment plot based on the standard 9 point scale (Subrahmanyam *et al.*, 1995) (Table 1 and 2). The Per cent Disease Index (PDI) was computed from the above scale by using the following formula (Wheeler, 1969).

Table 1. Disease rating scale for Late leaf spot disease (Subrahmanyam *et al.*, 1995)

Disease Score	Description	Disease severity (%)
1	No disease	0
2	Lesions present largely on lower leaves; no defoliation	1-5
3	Lesions present largely on lower leaves, very few on middle leaves defoliation of some leaflets evident on lower leaves	6-10
4	Lesions on lower and middle leaves but severe on lower leaves; defoliation of some leaflets evident on lower leaves	11-20
5	Lesions present on all lower and middle leaves; over 50 % defoliation of lower leaves	21-30
6	Severe lesions on lower and middle leaves; lesions present but less severe on top leaves; extensive defoliation of lower leaves defoliation of some leaflets evident on middle leaves	31-40
7	Lesions on all leaves but less severe on top leaves; defoliation of all lower and some middle leaves	41-60
8	Defoliation of all lower and middle leaves; severe lesions on top leaves; some defoliation of top leaves evident	61-80
9	Almost all leaves defoliated, leaving bare stems; some leaflets may remain, but show severe leaf spots	81-100

Table 2. Disease rating scale for rust disease (Subrahmanyam *et al.*, 1995)

Disease Score	Description	Disease severity (%)
1	No disease	0
2	Pustules sparsely distributed, largely on lower leaves	1-5
3	Many pustules on lower leaves, necrosis evident; very few pustule on middle leaves	6-10
4	Numerous pustules on lower and middle leaves; severe necrosis on lower leaves	11-20
5	Severe necrosis of lower and middle leaves; pustules may be present on top leaves, but less severe	21-30
6	Extensive damage to lower leaves; middle leaves necrotic, with dense distribution of pustules; pustules on top leaves	31-40
7	Severe damage to lower and middle leaves; pustules densely distributed on top leaves	41-60
8	100 % damage to lower and middle leaves; pustules on top leaves, which are severely necrotic	61-80
9	Almost all leaves withered; bare stems seen	81-100

Sum of all the numerical ratings

$$\text{PDI} = \frac{\text{Sum of all the numerical ratings}}{\text{Number of observations} \times \text{Maximum disease grade}} \times 100$$

Number of observations × Maximum disease grade

Result and discussion

The statistically significant differences were observed in respect of per cent disease intensity of LLS and Rust as well as dry pod and haulm yield of groundnut (Table 3 and 4 : Pooled data : 2016-17, 2017-18 and 2018-19). The treatment T₂ : Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS was found significantly superior in reducing the LLS and rust severity. The per cent disease intensity of late leaf spot at 60 DAS (24.16%) at 90 DAS (37.50%) and rust at 90 DAS (19.44%). The same treatment showed highest pod yield and haulm yield among all the treatments followed by T₁ : Seed treatment of Carbendazim @ 2 g/kg seed + Foliar spray of Mancozeb 2.0 g/(0.2%) at 40 and 65 DAS. However, T₆ : Seed treatment of Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds was least effective. The highest pod yield (1399.67 Kg/ha) and haulm yield (2729.67 Kg/ha) was recorded in seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS. These research findings are in agreement with the earlier workers Jadeja *et al.* (1999). They applied Hexaconazole (0.0025%) and Difenoconazole (0.0125%) at three times on 30, 45 and 60 days old plant to manage leaf spots and rust of groundnut and reported that the fungicides reduced leaf spot and rust disease incidence and increased the yields significantly. Hexaconazole treatment showed 71% increase in pod yield and 87% increase in fodder yield. Johnson and Subrahmanyam (2003) reported that on groundnut Hexaconazole (0.2%) fungicide recorded minimum Percent Disease Index (PDI) of 18.8% (LLS) and 18.5 % (Rust) and increased the pod and haulm yields by 43 and 41 per cent, respectively when sprayed two times on 60 and 75 days old plant. Nutsugah *et al.*, (2007) found that when Tebuconazole applied alone was effective in reducing leaf spot severity and it yielded significantly higher biomass and pod yields compared to most of the treatments. For management of late leaf spot by different fungicides, an experiment was carried out by Nath, *et al.*, (2013). They tested three fungicides with their prefix concentrations in *in vitro* condition. Among three, Tebuconazole (0.15%) gave best results and decrease per cent disease to 52.42 % and increased yield up to 67 % as compared to 37 % increase by Tebuconazole (0.10%). Mushrif, *et al.*, (2017) evaluated seven fungicides comprising of triazoles (Difenoconazole, Propiconazole, Tebuconazole and Bitertanol), Dithiocarbamate (Mancozeb), Benzimidazole (Carbendazim) and Phthalimide (Chlorothalonil) *in vitro* and *in vivo* against *Cercospora arachidicola* and *Cercosporidium personatum*, during the year 2008-09 and 2009-10. They found that Tebuconazole suppressed the germination at 50ppm of the spores of both the pathogens completely under *in vitro* conditions. The field experiments also showed that the Tebuconazole (0.1 per cent) was effective in registering least disease severity in terms of percent disease intensity, 13.67 and 15.07 for 2009 and 2010 periods and highest

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pod yield, 2295.92 and 2551.02 kg ha⁻¹ and haulm yield, 2716.84 and 3066.22 kg ha⁻¹ respectively for 2009 and 2010 periods.

Conclusion

The present investigation concluded that among all the treatments, Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS showed lowest disease severity against late leaf spot and rust diseases . Application of fungicidal sprays influenced the development of Late leaf spot and Rust and reduced its intensity.

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Table 3 Management of foliar fungal diseases of Groundnut with fungicides (Pooled data : 2016-17, 2017-18 and 2018-19)

Treat. Nos.	Treatment details	Late leaf spot (% PDI)								Rust (% PDI)			
		60 DAS				90 DAS				90 DAS			
		2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pool ed Mean	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pool ed Mean	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pool ed Mean
T ₁	Seed treatment of Carbendazim @ 2 g/kg seed + foliar spray of Mancozeb 2.0 g/ (0.2%) at 40 and 65 DAS	19.17	31.30	33.24	27.90	41.67	49.17	45.83	45.56	19.17	20.83	21.67	20.56
T ₂	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS	23.33	26.85	22.31	24.16	47.50	34.17	30.83	37.50	21.67	18.33	18.33	19.44
T ₃	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Pyraclostrobin 5% + Metiram 55% WG @ 2 g/L (0.12%) at 40 and 65 DAS	34.17	38.80	39.81	37.59	50.83	49.17	45.00	48.33	25.83	25.00	23.33	24.72
T ₄	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystobin 25% WG @ 1.32 g/L (0.035%) at 40 and 65 DAS	33.33	39.44	39.54	37.44	54.17	51.67	48.33	51.39	26.67	27.50	25.83	26.67
T ₅	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63% @ 2 g/L at 40 and 65 DAS	40.00	43.98	44.07	42.68	60.83	59.17	55.00	58.33	30.00	28.33	26.67	28.33
T ₆	Seed treatment of Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds	43.33	47.50	46.67	45.83	56.67	58.33	55.00	56.67	31.67	30.00	28.33	30.00
T ₇	Control (Water spray)	64.17	61.30	59.54	61.67	80.83	79.17	71.67	77.22	56.67	46.67	42.50	48.61
	SEm±	1.60	1.90	1.85	1.78	2.18	2.39	2.13	2.27	1.93	1.61	1.19	1.59
	CD at 5%	4.94	5.87	5.70	5.52	6.72	7.36	6.56	6.83	5.96	4.98	3.67	4.87

Table 4. Effect of fungicides on yield of Groundnut (Pooled data : 2016-17, 2017-18 and 2018-19)

Treat.Nos.	Treatment details	Pod yield Kg/ha				Haulm yield Kg/ha			
		2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pooled Mean	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	Pooled Mean
T ₁	Seed treatment of Carbendazim @ 2 g/kg seed + Spray of Mancozeb 2.0 g/ (0.2%) at 40 and 65 DAS	1370	1378	1386	1378.00	2777	2509	2812	2699.33
T ₂	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole @ 1ml/L (0.0259%) at 40 and 65 DAS	1345	1437	1417	1399.67	2738	2571	2880	2729.67
T ₃	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Pyraclostrobin 5% + Metiram 55% WG @ 2 g/L (0.12%) at 40 and 65 DAS	1147	1289	1348	1261.33	2302	2368	2709	2459.67
T ₄	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Tebuconazole 50% + Trifloxystobin 25% WG @ 1.32 g/L (0.035%) at 40 and 65 DAS	1078	1197	1319	1198.00	2140	2207	2633	2326.67
T ₅	Seed treatment with Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds + foliar spray of Carbendazim 12% + Mancozeb 63% @ 2 g/L at 40 and 65 DAS	1344	1244	1347	1311.67	2721	2433	2695	2616.33
T ₆	Seed treatment of Tebuconazole 2DS @ 1.5 g/kg seeds	1013	1183	1104	1100.00	1980	1980	2307	2089.00
T ₇	Control (Water spray)	959	963	1002	974.67	1930	1858	2023	1937.00
	SEm±	70.09	72.82	83.71	75.54	175.65	129.0	197.4	167.55
	CD at 5%	215.9	218.23	257.94	226.64	541.25	397.57	608.2	515..66